

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING THE PEDAGOGICAL METHOD OF THE "INSERT"
STRATEGY IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY PRACTICAL EXERCISES

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Abstract

is analyzed pedagogically . Based on the method of the "INSERT" strategy in scientific research, students can be taught to analyze texts, express their opinions, assimilate information by comparison, draw clear conclusions, and also form independent creative thinking skills . quality and efficiency significant showed that it has increased .

Key words : innovative methods , information technologies , "INSERT" strategy method .

to improve the pedagogical approaches used in the teaching of various subjects in higher education institutions, in order to interest students in subjects, to determine their possession of certain concepts and to form the skills of an analytical approach to textual information obtained from various sources. confirming the results [1]. Currently, one of such interactive pedagogical methods of teaching subjects is the "INSERT" strategy method, which is widely used in the educational process of educational institutions of most developed countries.

The "INSERT" strategy method was proposed by American psychologists D. Still, K. Meredith and Ch. Temple in the second half of the 90s of the 20th century. This method is used in critical thinking technology. The abbreviation INSERT, translated from English, means "**Interactive educational effective reading and thinking system**". The strategy serves to determine the students' possession of certain concepts related to the new topic to be mastered and to support their activity when working with the text. [2] .

Interactive English word is "interact": "inter" - mutually and "act" - action do), them when summarizing and " Interactive " - mutual movement to do the meaning means "Interaction" - cooperation (etc with) means . That is , teaching interactive methods - knowledge and communicative activity organize of reaching special shape being , then education receivers to know to the process attraction done they will be who knows and thinking things to understand and thinking opportunity have will be [3] .

Strategy apply the following in order done is increased :

- ❖ small groups is formed and is called
- ❖ each one from the group appropriation intended to the topic from 2 about thought notice is asked ;
- ❖ students queue with own comments statement they reach
- ❖ statement done thoughts writing will go ;
- ❖ then teacher new topic essence illuminant the text to groups distributes ;
- ❖ groups text with getting to know out , themselves stated of thoughts in the text information where level compatibility identify (similarity and differences special characters using note will be done);
- ❖ group members own personal their views statement enough and special characters the number can be summarized ;

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- ❖ group members from among leaders is determined ;
- ❖ each one leader own groups result with everything introduces ;
- ❖ of groups approaches generalization based on final conclusion is issued .

Strategy in application students the following to the scheme according to activities organize will :

Table 1.

Groups by reported thoughts with text comparative compared to :

Special characters	Special of characters meaning
Z	In the text groups by reported thoughts own on the contrary found if
S	In the text groups by reported thoughts own on the contrary did not find if
D	In the text to each other opposite thoughts there is if
?	Text with get to know in the process questions if born (misunderstandings surface if it comes)

Table 2.

Leaders from the report after of groups the results in learning this from the table used :

Special of characters order number	Groups names			
	Al Khorezmi	Beruni	G i p ocrat	Ali- Kushchi
1				
2				
3				
4				

Strategy in students makes sense thinking , personal errors on work skills to form help will give . Method "Understanding information. Types of information." Texts given to groups in the application of the subject in teaching .

Understanding of information. Types of information.

At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, new directions of science and the emergence of new disciplines led to a sharp increase in the amount of information required for processing. Automatic information processing devices created in the middle of the 20th century - electronic computing machines (ECMs) made it possible to store and classify large amounts of information and process them at high speed.

Informatics and information technology is a science that studies the methods of information representation, storage, transmission and processing with the help of EHM.

Information common to the definition have non imp e ric understanding Information what " d e gan to the question philosophy science " us wrapping category of being expression "d e b explains , from the information in practice users " information-storage" , form change and transmission possible has been it is an object " d e b explains .

of information the world in knowledge , society , work in release and in science place

Human creative or work activity , science and technology development , live of creatures himself to finish , har how automatic way working devices activity information exchange with depend

Information types

Text . The text is this information to express shape is , it is content single , whole and selected from the diversity of language features consists of Text document is the basis

Image . Image is it something event , event or processes in itself expressed picture pieces and of colors consists of is information . Photo , landscape , math e matic functions graph and that's it similar data is considered

Animation . Animation at a certain time images replacement is good . In this known time between , is known in the thigh one different to size have has been images are effective will be replaced .

Informatics Science is also different sciences in line the world to know for service does In the world each one live and lifeless creature in space and at the time changed category substance and power in the form of manifestation will be

Substance and power of the world two important content , its two important structural is part of L e kin of existence there is to be and him to know again one important and necessary content there is even if it is is information .

Information collection , storage and processing new technology

of exposure appear to be society in development revolutionary to changes reason it happened to a person information collection , storage and processing with depends has been mental work automation made it possible . This kind of processes automation economic and organizational systems , technology processes to manage projects make up , scientific research , study and another to areas come in went

Information 3 ways to code there is they are are as follows :

- 1) **Information graph in the form kodlsah** - in this different photo and from the forms used ;
- 2) **Information digital in the form coding** - numbers , algebraic expressions by means of ;
- 3) **Information symbolic coding** - of information initial appearance expressed alphabet signs using coding .

Ancient Roman emperor Julius Caesar is also of information confidentiality provide for the text coding method thinking found " Caesar cipher " in the text letter in the alphabet from himself after came the third to the letter replaced . In this alphabet circular in the form written , password prepared Coding this method " Alphabet push it is called " method " .

Remember let's go byte information measure being

1 byte = 8 bits,

1 K bytes = 1024 bytes ,

1 M bytes = 1024 K bytes ,

1 G byte = 1024 M bytes .

Above given in the example coding binary count in the system done So , count system of exposures arithmetical , logical and physicist basis organize is enough

The student monitors the activity of the groups during the training, gives advice to the group members in the necessary places, gives guidance and after making sure that the opinions given by the groups are in the right direction. ng asks the group leaders to summarize the ideas. Also, after each group leader finishes his opinion, the teacher helps the students to solve and understand the contradictions and misunderstandings that have arisen. Similar points identified by all subgroups are summarized [4] .

In Figure 3, on the basis of the concept of this method, pedagogical experiment - tests were conducted among the students of the parallel groups of the Asian International University of Treatment and Stomatology , and interactive methods, including the "INSERT" strategy method, were used in the experimental groups compared to the traditional lesson in the control groups. When used, the quality indicator of students' completion of lessons increased from 62.5% to 84.5% (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

In short, the "INSERT" strategy method teaches students to be able to analyze texts, express their opinions, assimilate information through comparison , draw clear conclusions, and also gave an opportunity to form independent creative thinking skills . The use of this method improves the quality and efficiency of the educational process by 21.9 % The results of the analysis showed that it is high .

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